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To cite this article: Simone Mancini *et al* 2024 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **2745** 012010

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Development and verification of a discrete event simulation tool for high-fidelity modelling of offshore wind and solar farm decommissioning campaigns

Simone Mancini, Jesse Bloothoofd, Vinit Dighe, Harald van der Mijle Meijer

TNO. Energy and Materials Transition Unit. Wind Energy group. Westerduinweg 3, 1755 LE Petten, the Netherlands

E-mail: simone.mancini@tno.nl

Abstract. The number of offshore wind turbines to be decommissioned is expected to grow in the next decade but some of the oldest wind farms in the North Sea region are already approaching the end of their service lives. This means that several detailed decommissioning plans will need to be prepared in the coming 2-5 years. So far, only small-scale wind farms consisting of relatively small turbines located in shallow, near-shore, or confined waters have been decommissioned. The limited experience and data available yield high uncertainty in the estimation of costs, duration, and environmental footprint of upcoming offshore wind farm decommissioning campaigns. High-fidelity logistic simulation tools as well as high-level cost models are both needed to support end-of-life decision-making. While several holistic cost models have been proposed, the literature lacks high-fidelity models to support the detailed planning and execution of offshore wind farm decommissioning projects. Given that offshore operations are the greatest source of costs, emissions, and safety risks in decommissioning campaigns, these require special attention when seeking optimization opportunities. In this work, a high-fidelity logistic simulation module for the decommissioning of offshore wind and solar farms has been developed within the discrete event simulation platform UWise. The new UWise Decommission module enables detailed assessment of alternative decommissioning scenarios taking into account offshore operation complexities like weather and resource dependencies, which are not included or heavily approximated in holistic cost models. The new tool has been verified against publicly available analytical cost model results from recent literature. A short assessment of the impact of weather delays on cost and duration estimates for the considered offshore wind farm decommissioning campaign has also been performed as an example of how UWise Decommission may bring value to the planning of offshore decommissioning projects.

1. Introduction

As some early commercial-scale offshore wind farms (OWFs) in the North Sea region are approaching their twentieth anniversary, offshore wind decommissioning and end-of-life (EoL) research is gaining more attention. Although the sharp increase in volumes is only expected in the next decade [1], a few detailed decommissioning plans will have to be prepared in the next 2-5 years. In the Netherlands for example, the 108MW Offshore Wind Egmond aan Zee (OWEZ [2]) and the 120MW Prinses Amalia [3] farms commissioned in 2007 and 2008, respectively, are nearing the expiry of their 20-year permits.

According to the 4C Offshore database [4], if single-turbine demo projects are excluded less than ten OWFs were decommissioned worldwide as of March 2023. The complete list is reported in Table 1. These past projects presented moderate technical challenges since most of the decommissioned wind farms consisted of relatively small turbines located in shallow waters near shore, with the only exception of two far offshore demo projects (i.e. Beatrice and Fukushima Forward), which anyhow consisted of two turbines only. Although there are many similarities with installation campaigns, the lessons learned from the decommissioning of the first hundred-megawatt scale OWFs will be key in reducing the cost and environmental footprint of future large-scale campaigns.

Table 1: List of OWF decommissioned worldwide as of March 2023 (excluding single-turbine pilot projects). Source: [4].

OWF name	Country	WTGs	Farm capacity [MW]	Shore distance [km]	Water depth [m]	Comments
Beatrice Demo	UK	2	10	25	45	Far offshore wind demo project
Blyth	UK	2	4	1.5	7.5	-
Fukushima Forward II	JP	2	12	20	120	Floating wind demo project
Irene Vor-rink	NL	28	16.8	-	2.5	In confined waters next to a dam
Kemin Ajoksen I&II	FI	10	30	2.6	7	Installed on artificial islands
Lely	NL	4	2	-	3.5	In confined waters
Utgrunden I	SE	7	10.5	5	10	-
Vindeby	DK	11	5	1.8	3	The world's first OWF
Yttre Sten-grund	SE	5	10	2.5	7	-

The limited experience and validation data available inevitably lead to high uncertainty in the estimation of OWF decommissioning cost [5, 6, 7]. Expected figures ranging from 250 k€/MW to 500 k€/MW have been proposed (e.g. [8, 9]), but the uniqueness of each project's specifications and requirements combined with the high sensitivity to vessel day rates make it hard to come up with generally applicable numbers. For example, foundations and balance of plant components may be removed fully, partially, or even left in situ depending on asset ownership, local regulations, and site-specific decisions. Therefore, estimates from different projects may be hard to compare even for farms of similar sizes and this further contributes to uncertainty. In this context, high-level holistic cost models and high-fidelity logistic tools are both needed to support OWF EoL decision-making and decommissioning campaign planning.

Several holistic cost models for OWF decommissioning have been developed and used in previous works. Two early examples are the EoL management support tool developed within the ODIN-Wind project [10], and the comprehensive cost model from DNV-GL [8], which was used to study the decommissioning requirements for potential offshore wind developments in the Great Lakes for the Ontario Ministry of the Environment and Climate Change [11]. A high-level Excel-based cost model was also developed to study the main operation parameters

affecting offshore wind decommissioning activities [5]. Significant cost differences were found when comparing the model results to the estimates reported in the decommissioning programme of the 315MW Sheringham Shoal OWF [12] in the United Kingdom (UK). More recently, an economic assessment framework for OWF decommissioning based on a detailed cost breakdown structure was developed to help wind farm owners and public authorities arrange appropriate financial provisions during the development phase [9]. Finally, extensive research was carried out within the 5-year DecomTools project aimed at reducing the cost and environmental footprint of offshore wind decommissioning campaigns in the North Sea region [13]. A holistic bottom-up cost model was developed in this project [7], and it was then applied to estimate costs and emissions of future decommissioning activities for three medium-size OWFs that are now operational in the North Sea [14, 15]. The study found the emission footprint to be significant for all cases and the cost estimates to suffer from high uncertainty due to the lack of experience and data available.

Similar cost models and decision-support frameworks are particularly useful in early planning phases to either prepare high-level decommissioning plans, or to estimate the amount of guarantees that the wind farm owner should arrange to cover future decommissioning activities. However, as OWFs grow older and approach the end of their useful life, more detailed decommissioning plans have to be prepared by the wind farm owner to start the procurement process or comply with regulation requirements [16]. Since offshore operations are the greatest source of costs, emissions, and safety risks in a decommissioning campaign [9, 17], special attention should be devoted to the design and selection of offshore methods, resources, and activities to identify optimization possibilities when drawing up detailed decommissioning plans. A similar task requires high-fidelity logistic models able to evaluate the effects of weather dependencies (e.g. weather windows, operational limits) and resource constraints (e.g. shift patterns) on offshore activities. The latter are typically neglected by lower-fidelity models, whereas the impact of weather delays is typically included as a fixed percentage penalty applied to the campaign cost or duration (e.g. [7, 11]) relying on empirical assumptions that carry high uncertainty.

High-fidelity logistic modelling tools are frequently applied in the detailed design of OWF installation campaigns. This is not yet the case for decommissioning due to the limited market size and experience. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the only offshore logistic simulations concerning OWF decommissioning were carried out in the DecomTools project, where alternative decommissioning scenarios for the Horn Rev I OWF (in the UK) were evaluated, and the sensitivity of costs and emissions to supply chain logistic parameters was investigated [18]. However, since the focus was on overall supply chain logistics (including onshore activities), offshore operations were aggregated into macro-activities without modelling the detailed method statements and using relatively coarse resolution (24h) for the weather data.

In this work, a new high-fidelity discrete event simulation tool that enables detailed modelling of offshore decommissioning campaigns has been developed aiming to fill the present gap in the literature. The model has been implemented as a new module in the Unified Wind farm Simulation Engine (UWiSE [19]) software platform developed by the Netherlands organization for applied scientific research (TNO) to simulate and optimize offshore wind farms logistics.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the new software module outlining its key inputs, outputs, and functionalities; Section 3 presents the results of a first model verification case comparing against estimates from the DecomTools project; Section 4 addresses the main conclusions and plans for future research.

2. Model description

The new UWiSE Decommission module has been developed within TNO's discrete-event simulation software platform UWiSE [19], which is introduced in Section 2.1. Then the UWiSE

Decommission module is described in Section 2.2 following its standard modelling workflow.

2.1. The UWiSE software platform

The Energy research Center of the Netherlands (ECN), which is now TNO, has been one of the pioneers of wind energy research and it has more than 20 years of experience in developing cost and decision-support models for offshore wind farm installation, and operation & maintenance (O&M). ECN’s O&M modelling activities began in the early 2000s and led to the development of commercial tools like the ECN O&M Tool [20], the ECN O&M Cost Estimator (OMCE [21]), and the ECN O&M Access [22]. These models have been very popular within the industry and contributed to the rapid growth of the wind energy sector in the Netherlands and abroad.

In 2017, TNO developed the UWiSE software [19] to bring the main ECN logistic models into a single platform, unifying the software logic, improving the user experience, and streamlining future development activities. UWiSE was created to support the industry in optimizing OWF construction, operations, and maintenance activities to bring down the cost of offshore wind projects. The software combines a discrete-event simulation engine backend with an interactive graphical frontend (fig. 1). The main frontend and backend features are listed below.

Figure 1: UWiSE software platform overview.

- **UWiSE backend:**

- discrete-event simulation logic based on next-event time progression;
- advanced work order scheduling logic accounting for activity dependencies, weather, and resource constraints (e.g. weather windows, operational limits, resource availability, shift patterns, permit periods, etc.);
- power production logic including models for wind turbine generators and solar photovoltaic (PV) plants, which also take inter-array cable string connections into account;
- stochastic event generation logic based on the Monte Carlo method to account for component failure modes and non-deterministic task durations;
- metocean data import routines;
- Excel output summary and simulation Gantt chart generation (see Section 2.2.3).

- **UWiSE frontend:**

- map-based graphical user interface (GUI) allowing visual review of the detailed input information (see Section 2.2.2);
- process editor whiteboard to create convenient block diagram descriptions of method statements, including task and resource dependencies, non-deterministic durations, operational limits, weather windows, iterations, learning curves, etc. (see Section 2.2.2);
- simulation setup tab to specify the run settings like simulation duration, random seeds, weather years, multi-core parallel execution, etc. (fig. 5b);
- Detailed, zoomable, and color-coded Gantt chart visualization of every simulation scenario.

UWiSE is constantly developed based on outcomes of joint research projects and feedback from industrial clients or partners. Four different application modules have been developed within the platform:

- **UWiSE Install** for high-fidelity modelling of offshore power plant installation campaigns. It can be used to evaluate the cost-benefit profile of alternative installation campaign scenarios (e.g. [23, 24, 25]).
- **UWiSE Decommission** for high-fidelity modelling of offshore power plant decommissioning campaigns. This new module is described in Section 2.2.
- **UWiSE O&M Planner** for high-fidelity modelling of the long-term operation and maintenance activities of offshore power plants. It allows, among other things, to evaluate and compare the operational expenditures (OPEX) associated with different O&M strategies (e.g. [26, 22, 27]).
- **UWiSE Despatch** for the optimal daily scheduling of maintenance activities on offshore wind farms. It can be used, for example, to automate the generation of daily transfer plans for an operating wind farm [28].

Each module in the UWiSE platform may be accessed via specific license agreements or joint development projects. Academic licenses may also be arranged for teaching or fundamental research purposes.

2.2. The UWiSE Decommission module

The newly developed UWiSE Decommission module has been designed to enable detailed modelling of offshore power plant decommissioning campaigns. Being part of the UWiSE platform, the new module benefits from the frontend and backend functionalities described in Section 2.1 allowing activities, resources, and weather dependencies to be taken into account in the discrete event simulations. The current version supports the modelling of worldwide decommissioning campaigns of offshore wind turbines, both bottom-fixed and floating, solar PV systems, and balance of plant (BOP) components including but not limited to foundations, scour protection, substations, export and inter-array cables, and met masts.

UWiSE Decommission users are free to define the scope of their offshore decommissioning campaign. The tool provides them with the flexibility to simulate full or partial removal scenarios of any assets or BOP components depending on their needs. Users are also free to decide what level of detail to include in the method statement description to be provided when preparing a simulation scenario. This flexibility makes UWiSE Decommission useful for a different range of applications, from the high-level modelling of the decommissioning campaign for estimating financial guarantees during wind farm development, to the detailed simulation of decommissioning projects in their planning and execution phases.

As a result, the target user group of UWiSE Decommission is also quite broad and it may include different functional teams within asset owner organizations, who are accountable for the decommissioning of their assets and need to prepare budgets, service tenders, and plans for these

campaigns, as well as offshore contractors who have to prepare service bids and detailed technical plans for offshore decommissioning projects. Research institutes (like TNO) may exploit the tool too, for example, to evaluate the impact of alternative processes or innovative equipment (e.g. pendulum versus feeder barge strategies, alternative cranes, low-emission floating heavy lift vessels, etc.) looking for ways to reduce the cost, duration, and environmental footprint of future OWF decommissioning campaigns.

Figure 2: UWiSE Decommission modelling workflow.

Figure 2 depicts the standard simulation workflow for a generic UWiSE Decommission scenario. Such a workflow consists of three phases, and the following sections briefly describe each of them: Section 2.2.1 covers the initial input definition; Section 2.2.2 describes the use of the GUI to review the inputs and define the method statement; Section 2.2.3 covers the different outputs of the tool.

2.2.1. Inputs In the first phase of UWiSE Decommission’s modelling workflow, two project input files have to be prepared:

- (i) **the Excel input file.** For a specific decommissioning project, most input parameters, including the types of assets to be modelled and the resources available, are supplied through an Excel input file. This file comprises 14 sheets, each featuring predefined cells to be filled in by the user. Conceptually, these input sheets can be grouped into three main categories:
 - *project information*, including basic project-specific inputs like the farm layout, available ports, metocean locations, project fixed costs, permit periods, and special vessel routes;
 - *assets*, covering all input information on the energy-producing assets (i.e. wind turbines and solar PV systems) and BOP, including the component breakdown whose level of detail is entirely up to the user. It is also possible to specify whether any of the assets are still producing electricity at the start of the simulation and what is their power rating (i.e. de-rated assets can be modelled).
 - *resources*, covering costs, performance, shift patterns, and availability information for the resources included in the scenario (i.e. vessels, technician teams, equipment, and storage locations).

The complete list of input sheets is given in fig. 3. Here it is noted that not all input fields are mandatory and the user can decide whether to include them or not depending on the scope of the analysis. All cells in the input Excel file are color-coded to distinguish necessary inputs from elective ones.

- (ii) **The metocean parameters table.** This table (to be provided in a .csv format) contains the time series of all the weather parameters specified in the "Metocean" sheet of the Excel input file. These parameters can be used for the definition of operational limits (e.g. weather windows and safety constraints) as well as for the calculation of the energy generated by the active assets in the farm (if any). There is no length requirement for the weather input time series. The longer is the list compared to the simulation duration (specified through the GUI), the more starting weather years will be available for selection when tuning the run settings (step iii in Section 2.2.2). Also, as long as the metocean table format is respected, the tool accepts data from any (combination of) weather parameter sources regardless if it is forecast or hindcast data from models or measurements.

Figure 3: List of all the sheets in the UWise Decommission Excel input file.

2.2.2. User interface: input review and process editor Once the input Excel file and the metocean parameters table have been prepared, the user uploads them to the GUI and starts the second phase of the simulation workflow, which is carried out entirely through the GUI (alternatively, a command line interface is available for scripting but it shall be considered non-standard workflow and therefore it is not described here).

The UWise GUI is organized into 4 tabs (i.e. user view panels): the Projects tab listing all the open projects (top panel in fig. 4); the Inputs tab summarizing all input information provided by the user (left panel in fig. 4); the Process tab that opens a whiteboard where the block-diagram description of the method statement can be entered (see fig. 5a); the Simulations tab where the latest simulation runs are listed and the corresponding outputs can be opened.

This phase of the standard modelling workflow involves three main steps:

- (i) **inputs review.** When the two input files of Section 2.2.1 are uploaded to the GUI, an interactive map-based view of the scenario is generated to facilitate the review of the main input parameters (fig. 4). This step is key when generating detailed scenarios as the large amount of data to be entered in the Excel input file makes the task prone to errors.
- (ii) **Process description.** The Process tab in the GUI opens an interactive process editor, i.e. an editable whiteboard where block-diagram descriptions of offshore decommissioning campaigns can be conveniently created by adding, customizing, and interconnecting different process blocks (fig. 5a).

There are more than 15 types of blocks available, each one representing a specific activity (e.g. transits, work, transferring of personnel, etc.). To structure the process description,

Figure 4: Snapshot of the Inputs tab in the UWiSE GUI for the Lincs OWF decommissioning scenario.

the user can define multiple levels in the process diagram by grouping chains of activities into parent blocks. In fig. 5a, for example, three parent blocks are defined in the first level of the diagram by grouping the wind turbine, foundation, and substation removal activities and providing a detailed description of each campaign using child blocks in lower levels of the diagram.

Blocks are editable and depending on their type (i.e. which activity they represent) a number of block-specific input parameters can be specified, only some of which are mandatory. Typical block inputs are:

- *process step parameters* like activity durations (which can be stochastic or deterministic) or process iterations (repetitive activities for which learning curves can be defined);
- *resource dependencies*, i.e. what entities (vessels, technicians, equipment) among those specified in the Excel input file are involved in the activity;
- *block-specific restrictions* due to weather (e.g. operational limits, weather windows) or permit constraints.

Process interdependencies (e.g. serial or parallel activities) are specified by connecting different blocks. No constraint is set to the number of blocks to be defined in the process diagram. Therefore, any method statement, however detailed, can be described by assembling individual blocks in the process editor whiteboard.

Note that the block diagram defines the scope of the decommissioning campaign to be simulated. Hence, the user has to specify which assets or BOP components are removed by adding specific blocks in the process editor.

(iii) **Tuning the simulation settings.** Once the process description is finalized, the user may

tune the final settings before simulating the scenario (fig. 5b). These include:

- *random seed settings*, which are only relevant when non-deterministic activity durations are specified in the process blocks, to ensure results reproducibility;
- *simulation settings*, like the simulation length, the target date for identifying the campaign's latest possible start week, the number of threads for parallel execution, and the weather starting years to be considered in the simulations. The weather years available for selection depend on the length of the metocean parameters table uploaded (Section 2.2.1).

Figure 5: (a) Snapshot of the first level of blocks defined in the process description of the Lincs OWF decommissioning verification scenario. (b) Snapshot of the simulation settings tab of UWiSE Decommissioning.

2.2.3. Outputs The third and final phase of the standard modelling workflow involves the processing of the model outputs. For every simulation, UWiSE Decommissioning generates three different types of output, which may or may not be relevant to the user depending on the analysis to be performed. These are:

- **Simulation log files.** For each individual run (i.e. for each random seed and weather starting year considered), a log file recording all discrete events that occurred in the simulation is generated to ensure full transparency and traceability of results. Although log files are human readable and might be useful to check specific simulation details (e.g. for debugging purposes), the large amount of events recorded requires post-processing scripts to extract relevant information from the data stored in these files. For example, the two model outputs described below are both automatically derived from the log files at the end of each simulated scenario. Whenever custom information that is not included in the Excel summary output file or the Gantt chart is needed, this can be obtained by processing the data contained in the log files.
- **An Excel summary output file.** For each simulated scenario, the tool generates a detailed summary output file in Excel format containing an extensive list of indicators including detailed breakdowns of the project costs, duration, resource utilization, and delays. The file consists of three overview sheets providing aggregate results from the full spectrum of simulations performed, plus additional summary sheets characterizing each

weather starting year considered separately. The aggregate quantities in the overview sheets are calculated from all the random seeds and weather years so that average output values are accompanied by statistical parameters (including minimum, maximum, P50, and P90), which define the uncertainty associated with each output quantity.

- **Interactive Gantt charts.** For each individual run (i.e. for each random seed and weather starting year considered), a detailed simulation Gantt chart is generated and can be opened through the GUI. Figure 6 shows a Gantt chart snapshot from one of the Lincs scenario simulations discussed in Section 3. In the GUI, the chart is color-coded to aid the visual interpretation of the events occurring along the timeline, and it can be zoomed from the full campaign duration down to the hourly scale. The tool also allows the timeline to be broken down into individual activities (i.e. specific blocks defined in the process description) for detailed reviews.

Figure 6: Snapshot of the interactive Gantt chart from one of the weather starting years simulated in the Lincs OWF decommissioning verification scenario.

3. Results

The first version of UWise Decommission has been released in October 2023. Being a new module, validation and verification of its results is paramount to enable its exploitation. Due to the lack of validation data publicly available, a first model verification case has been considered in this work. By verification it is meant checking that the discrete event algorithm implementation works as intended [29]. In practice, this entails comparing against other numerical model results to verify whether the new UWise Decommission module yields the expected output.

A well-documented decommissioning scenario for the Lincs OWF has been considered as the benchmark for this first verification case. The Lincs OWF was installed in 2013 about 8km off the coast of Skegness in the east coast of England and it consists of 75 x 3.6MW turbines with a 120m rotor diameter. The farm is currently operational but a high-level decommissioning scenario for the wind turbine generators (WTGs), foundations, and the offshore substation (OS) was devised and modelled in the DecomTools project [13], starting from the publicly available decommissioning plan prepared during wind farm development [30]. Cost and emission footprint for this scenario were estimated using a holistic analytical cost model that was developed in the same project [7].

Although the official decommissioning plan was used as a guideline, the DecomTools scenario applied several cost and process parameter variations that resulted in substantial differences between the two sets of estimates (>50% variations in vessel utilization and up to ~30% in costs [15]). The official decommissioning plan did not provide a detailed enough description of the inputs and outputs of the cost model to replicate its results, therefore only the DecomTools

project scenario described in [15] has been used as a benchmark for the verification of UWiSE Decommission results.

It is important to point out that the benchmark decommissioning process description from the DecomTools project is rather high-level, in line with the holistic perspective of the analytical model that was used. For example, generic vessels and equipment were considered without accounting for specific technical limitations that might impose changes to the proposed method statements. Moreover, the report considers a vessel transit distance of just 8km as if the decommissioning port was located in the nearest town of Skegness, whereas the closest industrial harbours are located more than 40km away from the farm (e.g. in King's Lynn, Grimsby, or Hull). These simplifications combined with the uncertainty associated with the assumed vessel day rates and activity durations make the results presented in this section solely intended for numerical model verification. The decommissioning campaign costs and duration figures hereinafter reported should be treated with care and not taken as reference values for the Lincs OWF decommissioning. More detailed simulations would be needed to get more accurate and realistic estimates.

The results of the Lincs OWF verification case are discussed below in Section 3.1. Subsequently, Section 3.2 presents a brief sensitivity analysis as an example of how the new UWiSE Decommission module's capabilities may be leveraged to support detailed planning of OWF decommissioning campaigns.

3.1. Results verification

As a first verification case for the UWiSE Decommission module the removal of WTGs, foundations, and the OS of the Lincs OWF have been considered. To maximize consistency between the DecomTools model parameters and the UWiSE Decommission inputs, the same method statements, activity durations, and vessel day rates as reported in [15] have been prescribed in the UWiSE Decommission simulations.

Due to the different fidelity levels of the benchmark model and UWiSE not all differences could be eliminated. An attempt has been made, however, to minimize these differences by neglecting all elective input details that are typically included in UWiSE simulations (e.g. activity durations have been modelled as deterministic, technicians have been assumed always available for work, no costs other than vessel day rates have been considered, permit restrictions have been neglected). The modelling of the Lincs OWF layout (see fig. 4) and of the weather delays were the main outstanding sources of discrepancy between UWiSE Decommission and the DecomTools estimates. While in DecomTools weather delays were modelled as a fixed percentage increase (i.e. 20%) of the estimated campaign duration, UWiSE calculates them based on user-specified metocean parameter time histories (Section 2.2.1), weather windows, and operational limits that can be applied to the activities defined in the block-based process description (Section 2.2.2).

Luckily, for the sake of model verification, such a difference could be avoided by comparing results for the "perfect weather" (PW) case, i.e. a reference case where all weather dependencies are neglected and thus no weather delay occurs.

Figure 7 compares the total duration of each sub-campaign obtained with UWiSE Decommission (plotted in orange) with the DecomTools estimates (plotted in blue). For each sub-campaign, the lower pair of bars represents the PW case.

The largest duration difference of the PW results has been found for the WTGs removal where UWiSE estimates a 1.7% longer campaign duration than the benchmark. This discrepancy can be explained by the fact that the DecomTools calculation neglected the additional duration due to the offloading of the last WTGs at the port, which are critical path activities and thus have been included in the UWiSE Decommission estimate. WTG offloading activities added about 70.5h to the UWiSE estimate, 36h due to the unloading of the last three WTGs plus 34.5h of

Figure 7: Comparison of the Lincs OWF decommissioning sub-campaign duration estimates from UWiSE Decommission and the DecomTools results [15] for the expected (i.e. including weather delays) and perfect weather cases (PW, i.e. excl. weather delays).

lag caused by the unloading of the previous batch of 9 WTGs not being finished before the other barge vessel (BV) with the last 3 WTGs reached the quayside. The remaining difference (~5h) is a result of the transits to/from the port and between individual turbines in the farm, which have been considered in UWiSE and neglected in DecomTools. Similarly, the PW OS removal duration estimated with UWiSE Decommission has been found ~1h longer than the benchmark due to the two transits of the jack-up vessel (JUV) considered in UWiSE only. Finally, the PW foundations removal results have also been affected by similar differences, namely the unloading of the last batch of monopiles at the port and the transits of the JUV being accounted for in UWiSE Decommission only. However, these have been largely compensated by the lower overall transit duration of the offshore support vessel (OSV). The benchmark assumed OSV transits to add 0.25h per WTG (i.e. 18.75h in total) whereas in UWiSE, where transit durations are calculated based on the farm layout coordinates and vessel speed specified in the Excel input file, these accounted for just ~5h in total (as in the WTGs removal campaign).

Besides the PW case, fig. 7 also reports the expected duration of each sub-campaign accounting for weather delays. While the DecomTools estimates are obtained by simply increasing the PW duration by 20%, the UWiSE Decommission bars depict the expected value of twenty-three simulations¹ using different hourly hindcast wind and wave time series from year 1994 to 2016. Local wind speed data was sourced from the ERA5 database [31], and the time histories of significant wave height at the Lincs OWF location were obtained from the North Sea Wave Database [32].

To estimate the impact of weather delays in UWiSE, generic operational limits have been specified for the three vessel types used in the reference decommissioning scenario, i.e. a JUV, an OSV, and two BVs towed by tug boats (TB). The assumed weather limits per vessel type are

¹ The total run time for the whole simulation set (i.e. PW + 23 weather year) was less than 1min on a 2022 laptop featuring a 12-threads processor.

reported in Table 2. Moreover, an arbitrary but customary 50% relative weather window has been applied to all offshore activities (meaning that a 1.5h window of favorable weather would be needed for a 1h activity to start) with the only exception of the monopile cutting, where a fixed weather window equal to the task duration has been applied due to the multi-day span of the activity.

Table 2: Generic vessel weather limits used in UWise Decommission simulations.

vessel type	max wind (@10m) [m/s]	max H_s [m]
JUV	16	3
OSV	16	2.5
BV + TB	16	1.5

Here it is noted that, in UWise Decommission, the expected duration of the individual sub-campaigns reported in fig. 7 have been estimated by simulating each campaign independently from the others and always assuming March 1st as the start date. This start date was selected as reasonably representative of the whole weather year based on the analysis of Section 3.2.

The expected sub-campaign durations comparison reveals how, for the given site and decommissioning process description, the assumption of a 20% duration increase due to weather delays is likely too optimistic. The UWise Decommission estimates based on hindcast weather data exceed the DecomTools report values by ~10.5% for the removal of WTGs, ~38% for the OS, and ~30% for the foundations. Of course, these estimates are strictly linked to the somewhat arbitrary weather limits and windows that have been assumed in the simulations, but it is deemed unlikely that expected duration estimates will reduce substantially once method statements are refined and specific resource limitations are taken into account.

Figure 8: Comparison between the UWise Decommission and DecomTools report [15] estimates for the Lincs OWF decommissioning scenario, in terms of: (a) expected sub-campaign costs; (b) use of vessels in the foundations' removal sub-campaign.

The longer durations directly translate into greater expected costs for each sub-campaign as shown in fig. 8a since the resources (only vessels in this simple scenario) have to be hired for longer periods. In particular, the largest cost increase (of 34.6%) compared to the DecomTools

estimates is found for the foundations' removal as a result of a significantly higher number of working days expected for the JUV (+43.8%) and OSV (+27.3%) used in that campaign (fig. 8b).

Figure 9: Variation of the total expected cost of the Lincs OWF decommissioning scenario as a function of the campaign start date.

3.2. UWiSE Decommission application example: cost sensitivity to the campaign start date

After having verified the model results for the Lincs OWF decommissioning scenario in the PW case, the sensitivity of total expected decommissioning cost estimates to the campaign's start date has been investigated. This analysis has been included here as a brief example of a possible UWiSE Decommission use case, which is representative of a real-life application.

For this analysis, the same decommissioning scenario as presented in the previous section has been simulated, again considering the same 23 years of local wind and wave data. The only difference compared to the previous results is that the full Lincs OWF decommissioning campaign has been modelled in each simulation, assuming that the three sub-campaigns are performed in series. Note that this has no effect on the PW results but it affects the estimates that include weather delays, as each sub-campaign starts as soon as the previous one finishes and thus it is subject to different weather conditions than the isolated case (when the start date of each simulation was set to March 1st).

The full campaign simulation, consisting of 23 individual runs (one per weather year), has been repeated 12 times to investigate the total expected decommissioning cost sensitivity to different start dates. Each time the simulation start has been set to the first day of a different month.

The statistical results are shown in the box plot in fig. 9, where for each starting month:

- the box encompasses the cost range between the first and third quartile (of the 23 weather years output dataset);
- the line inside the box represents the median of the dataset;
- the circles represent outliers, which are defined as data points more than one inter-quartile range lower than the first quartile or higher than the third quartile;
- the whiskers indicate the dataset range excluding the outliers.

The box plot shows that decommissioning cost estimates for this specific scenario are highly sensitive to the period in which the activities are carried out. In this case, the best starting period is between April and June where not only the expected costs are the lowest, but the variance of the results between the different weather years is also minimal. Low cost but slightly higher variability is found starting in March and July. The last three months of the year are considerably worse as a large portion of weather-critical operations (part of both WTGs and foundations' removal campaigns) occur in winter time and thus cause long and expensive delays. In all three months, the median of the total expected decommissioning cost is about 30% higher than in the most favourable months.

4. Conclusions

A new discrete event simulation tool has been developed to support high-fidelity modelling of offshore decommissioning campaigns. The tool has been devised to support asset owners and contractors in the preparation of detailed decommissioning plans for offshore wind and solar farms, as well as research institutes to evaluate innovative concepts to reduce the cost, duration, environmental impact, and risk associated with these campaigns. The new module, named UWise Decommission, has been implemented within TNO's offshore logistic software platform UWise [19], which uses a next-event time progression logic to minimize computational costs while retaining accuracy.

Unlike the holistic cost models available in the literature, UWise Decommission simulates offshore campaigns in time with high fidelity, allowing uncertainties due to weather, activities, and resource availability to be taken into account when estimating costs, duration, and environmental impact of offshore decommissioning projects. In its current version, the module supports the modelling of worldwide decommissioning campaigns of offshore wind turbines, both bottom-fixed and floating, solar PV systems, and balance of plant (BOP) components including but not limited to foundations, scour protection, substations, export and inter-array cables, and met masts. The tool also allows accounting for energy production revenues from any potential asset still operational.

UWise Decommission has been designed to be flexible so the user has complete freedom to define the scope of the decommissioning scenario under consideration so that full or partial removal of any asset or BOP components can be simulated. The level of detail can also be tailored to the user's needs, as the offshore method statement to be simulated can be aggregated into large work packages or broken down into individual activities. This makes the tool useful for a wide range of applications, from the high-level modelling of decommissioning campaigns for budgeting to the detailed simulation of offshore decommissioning projects in their planning and execution phases.

As a first verification case, UWise Decommission results for a high-level decommissioning scenario of the Lincs OWF in the UK have been compared against publicly available analytical cost model results from the DecomTools project [15]. The comparison of the WTGs, foundations, and OS campaign duration in perfect weather (i.e. neglecting weather delays) showed a good agreement, with maximum differences below 2%. These minor discrepancies are attributed to the modelling of the last offloading activities at port and of vessel transits, both of which differed

between the models. A further simplification of the UWise scenario (i.e. removing offloading activities from the method statement and condensing the farm layout to a single point location) would eliminate these differences.

Expected decommissioning campaign cost and duration estimates including weather delays have also been compared for the Lincs OWF. While a flat 20% duration increase was used in DecomTools to account for weather uncertainty, the UWise Decommission estimates have been obtained by defining generic but customary operational limits and weather windows to the offshore activities, and by considering 23 years of hourly hindcast wind and wave data at the Lincs OWF site. The comparison results suggest that the 20% duration increase assumption is likely too optimistic for this site, with the expected cost estimates obtained with UWise Decommission being from 10.5% to 38% higher than the reference, under the assumptions made.

Finally, the sensitivity of the expected decommissioning cost estimates to the campaign start date has been investigated as an example of a possible UWise Decommission use case. The results have shown that, under the assumptions made, the total decommissioning campaign costs vary more than 30% between starting on the second or the last quarter of the year. As expected, the uncertainty bounds around the cost estimates also increase significantly in the least favourable starting months.

Although UWise is a mature software platform with a long validation and verification track record, the UWise Decommission module has just been developed and the validation of its results against field data from actual OWF decommissioning projects is key to enable its exploitation and it is therefore set as a priority for future work. While waiting for the right opportunity to get access to validation data, a more detailed decommissioning baseline scenario will be defined for the Lincs OWF to then estimate the potential impact of innovative process and equipment variations on the overall cost, duration, and emission footprint of this reference campaign.

Acknowledgments

The work described in this paper has been carried out within the EoLO-HUBs project (<https://www.eolo-hubs.eu/>) co-funded by the European Union (Agreement No. 101096425 - EoLO-HUBs - HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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